

Synthesis of Cycloheptazoline

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A 4-step synthesis of cycloheptazoline, a derivative of heptazoline, a carbazole alkaloid has been reported starting from 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole to substantiate the structure of heptazoline.

In the previous communication¹, we have reported the details of the structure of heptazoline (1), $C_{18}H_{17}NO_3$ (M^+ 295), m.p. 212-140°, a carbazole alkaloid isolated from *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn., the structure of which was supported by the synthesis of cycloheptazoline (2)^{2,3} obtained by cyclisation of 1 with polyphosphoric acid. Recently the synthesis of heptazoline has been reported by Kapil *et al.*⁴. This prompts us to report the details of synthesis of cycloheptazoline accomplished by synthetic route other than already reported¹.

1645 (C=O), 1610 and 1530 cm^{-1} (Ar system). 4 was dehydrogenated with Pd/C in paracymene to yield the carbazole (5) 2,1-(2',2'-dimethylpyran-4'-one)-3-methyl-8-hydroxycarbazole (5), m.p. 220-22° (homogeneous to tlc); λ_{max} (EtOH) 240, 260 and 282 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.69, 4.65 and 4.15); ν_{max} 3480 (NH), 3250 (OH), 1640 (C=O), 1610 and 1510 cm^{-1} (Ar system). 5 was reduced by Clemmensen reduction to indolochroman (6), $C_{18}H_{19}NO_3$, m.p. 180-82°; λ_{max} 255 and 282 ($\log \epsilon$ 4.55 and 4.32) ν_{max} 3480 (NH), 3240 (OH), 1610 and 1570 cm^{-1} (Ar system). 6 was oxidised with chromic acid when 2 was obtained,

(i) PPA, (ii) β,β -dimethylacrylic acid, $ZnCl_2$, $POCl_3$,
(iii) Pd/C, (iv) Clemmensen reduction, (v) oxidation.

In the synthesis of 2, the precursor chromanone with a potential hydroxyl function of 8-position of carbazole nucleus was accomplished following the method used in the synthesis of girinimbine⁵. For the preparation of the appropriate chromanone 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole (3) on treatment with β,β -dimethylacrylic acid in presence of zinc chloride and phosphorus oxychloride furnished 2,1-(2',2'-dimethylpyran-4'-one)-3-methyl-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole, $C_{18}H_{19}NO_3$ (4), m.p. 160-61°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 237 and 275 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.22 and 4.29); ν_{max} 3480 (NH),

$C_{18}H_{17}NO_3$, m.p. 286-91°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 239, 275 and 297 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.65, 4.62 and 4.39); ν_{max} 3226 (NH), 2924, 1699 (CHO), 1616 and 1575 cm^{-1} ; identical with 2 obtained by cyclisation of 1 with polyphosphoric acid.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The samples were dried *in vacuo* before analysis at 78°.

2,1-(2',2'-Dimethylpyran-4'-one)-3-methyl-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole (4): A mixture of 3 (3 g)

and β,β -dimethylacrylic acid (3 g) was treated with a mixture of phosphorus oxychloride (10 g) and zinc chloride (10 g) and kept at room temperatures for 24 h. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-water and worked up to get **4** (2 g) m.p. 160-61°, (Found: C, 72.74; H, 6; N, 4.75. $C_{18}H_{18}NO_3$ calcd. C, 72.72; H, 6.44; N, 4.70%); tlc (C_6H_6 - $CHCl_3$ - MeOH) Rf 0.68.

2,1-(2',2'-Dimethylpyran-4'-one)-3-methyl-8-hydroxycarbazole (5): **4** (2 g) in *p*-cymene (5 ml) and 10% palladised charcoal (25 mg) was dehydrogenated at 274° in a constant boiling solvent for 5 h. A brown gummy residue obtained was chromatographed over silica gel. C_6H_6 - $CHCl_3$ eluent on work up furnished the product, $C_{18}H_{17}NO_3$ (1.5 g), m.p. 220-22° (Found: C, 73.38; H, 5.68; N, 4.63. $C_{18}H_{17}NO_3$ calcd. C, 73.20; H, 5.80; N, 4.74%); tlc (C_6H_6 - AcOH, 95 : 5) Rf 0.51.

2,1-(2',2'-Dimethylpyran)-3-methyl-8-hydroxycarbazole (6): **5** (2.1 g) in a mixture of ethanol (25 ml), acetic acid (10 ml) and concentrated HCl (30 ml) containing amalgamated zinc (20 g) was kept at room temperature for 2 days, after which the reaction mixture was heated on water-bath for 1 h and then refluxed for 8 h with addition of HCl (20 ml) and ethanol (20 ml). After work up, a gummy residue was obtained, the benzene solution of which was filtered through a silica gel column. The filtrate on concentration furnished **6**, m.p. 180-82° (Found: C, 76.61; H, 6.63; N, 4.66.

$C_{18}H_{18}NO_2$ calcd. C, 76.84; H, 6.81; N, 4.98%); tlc (C_6H_6 - AcOH, 95 : 5) Rf 0.66.

Cycloheptazoline (2): **6** (500 mg) in CS_2 (5 ml) was reacted with chromyl chloride (2 g) in CS_2 (10 ml). The reaction was shaken for 90 min and after careful work up of the reaction product, a crystalline product, m.p. 286-9°, was obtained which was identified with cycloheptazoline prepared from heptazoline, by direct comparison of m.p., uv and ir spectra.

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